

CDC ROUND UP

SEPTEMBER- DECEMBER 2024

UNIVERSITY OF
LIVERPOOL

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The LCR Residents' Assembly on Data and AI Innovation Launches

In March 2025, the LCR Civic Data Cooperative is inviting 60 residents to debate the direction of data and AI innovation in the region. The CDC's mission is to make data about the region work for the people who live here. For our next project, we are building a set of principles, deliberated by residents, on what trustworthy and beneficial data innovation looks like, that could be used to help inform future local projects that use data with an impact on people's lives. We will use their recommendations to ratify a Liverpool City Region Data and AI Innovation Charter, one of the first of its kind in the world. This will give innovators and researchers in the region an actionable social license for data and AI innovation.

On Thursday 7th November we hosted the LCR Residents' Assembly on Data and AI Innovation Launch Meeting, bringing together key stakeholders, local community group leaders, researchers and academics. We care about your opinion and if you are looking to get involved or would like more information please email gracer@liverpool.ac.uk.

Community Data Hackathon

The CDC organised a one-day data hackathon in the Municipal Hotel in Liverpool on 6th December. The theme for this was 'Community through Data.' The event attracted a diverse group of people who share a passion for data and a desire to network, collaborate and create.

The CDC provided the backdrop to the day with a short panel discussion about the 'Round 'Ere' project undertaken in Widnes, with input from the CDC team, our collaborators at Capacity and one of the RE Community Researchers. This community approach, coupled with the datasets provided, gave the hackathon teams impetus and inspiration to spend the day compiling insights and ideas. The day culminated with enthusiastic and diverse pitches from each team, with a winner and runner announced. The CDC will utilise the insights and feedback from the event to shape and tailor another hackathon, which will take place in the Spring of 2025.

Image: Hackathon attendees

Gary Leeming visits Taiwan and Japan

Gary Leeming, the CDC Director, visited Taiwan in September and Japan in December, representing the CDC on both occasions.

In Taiwan, he participated in an international seminar where he delivered a joint talk with Professor Iain Buchan on Civic Data Engineering for Health Science Embedded in Health Services. He also joined a roundtable panel on Building a Patient-Centered Genomic and Health Data Governance Ecosystem and attended a closed meeting with the Taiwan Ministry of Health and Welfare, where he presented an Introduction to Health Information Engineering in Civic Health Data Innovation Labs. Additionally, he visited the Taiwan Biobank to further engage with local health data initiatives.

In Japan, Gary attended a reception organized by the British Council, which aimed to highlight and strengthen the existing networks between the UK and Japan. The event celebrated successful UK-Japan collaborations in higher education, such as RENKEI, and sought to foster deeper relationships and promote further academic and human exchanges between the two countries. He later traveled to Yamagata to participate in a RENKEI conference focused on health technologies.

The team look forward to more global partnerships and engagement in the coming year.

Community of Practice

The Civic Data Cooperatives' Community of Practice on Participatory and Inclusive Data Stewardship group met in Manchester at the People's History Museum on Monday 30th September. Following a tour of the museum the group discussed Inclusivity in Data and Participation.

The next meeting will be held remotely in January 2025. This session will be a 'Data Participation gallery.' If you would like to get involved, please contact the team.

Best Practice Guide on Digital Commons

CDC's Gary Leeming has worked with Angela Daly, Riccardo Nani and Mathieu O'Neil on a recently published blogpost with the National Centre for Academic and Cultural Exchange (NCACE) on the DCPC best practices guide for digital commons-government relations.

<https://ncace.ac.uk/2024/10/14/incorporating-digital-commons-into-government-policies-an-introduction-to-the-digital-commons-policy-councils-best-practices-guide/>

Award Winners

The CDC team received an award at the University of Liverpool Learning and Teaching Awards presentation this month. We were recognised for our contribution to 'Play your Part' which was a Students in the Community Initiative in 2023.

Participation, People and Power in Data and AI

The CDC were involved in organising a two-day workshop at Ness Botanical Gardens in Wirral. This event was co-convened by Elgon Social, Digital Good Network and Liverpool Civic Data Cooperative. The theme of the workshop was 'Participation, People and Power in Data and AI.' Emily Rempel, Research Fellow in Public Participation and Data Practices, who leads the participation work at the CDC commented 'It has been an inspiring two days discussing participatory work happening across the UK on data and AI. A massive thank you to Reema Patel for convening us and designing the sessions! And thank you everyone who joined us at the beautiful Ness Botanical Gardens. On behalf of LCR Civic Data Cooperative, we can't wait to see you all again!'

We are working alongside the team at The Brixham Data Trust organising our next in-person event in Brixham in March 2025.

Image: Poster created by a group at the CoP on Public Perception of Data.

Meet the Team: Erin McCloskey

Meet our very own Dr. Erin McCloskey, who has built an impressive public health research and policy career. Originally from Minneapolis, Minnesota, she now serves as the Postdoctoral Research Associate in Public Participation for the Civic Data Cooperative and as work package 6 lead for the DynairX project which focuses on engaging with the public and incorporating the public's views within the research. Her academic journey began at the University of St. Thomas in St. Paul, Minnesota, where she earned an undergraduate degree in International Studies and French.

After graduating, Erin spent a year and a half teaching in the Picardie region of France before returning to the University of St. Thomas to pursue a Master of Arts in International Leadership and Public Policy. Alongside her studies, she worked as a Programme Manager for the Department of International Partnerships, leading student recruitment trips to Hong Kong, Vietnam, and Tanzania, as well as serving as an advisor to student trips to Venezuela and Mexico.

Erin's passion for global health led her to King's College London, where she earned a Master of Science in Global Mental Health, focusing on women's reproductive mental health. Her dissertation explored how parents of stillborn babies investigate the causes of death which inspired her to pursue this topic for her doctoral research. She went on to complete her PhD at Canterbury Christ Church University, working closely with their midwifery department to study how bereaved parents access peer support groups to support their grief journeys. Following this, Erin relocated to Runcorn with her husband and completed postdoctoral work where she served as the qualitative lead on the PLANES (Placental Growth Factor led Management of the Small for Gestational Age Fetus) Study within the Department of Public Health Policy and Systems at University of Liverpool.

Now at the CDC, Erin combines her diverse expertise in public health, mental health, and policy to drive impactful research and public engagement initiatives. Her career reflects a deep commitment to improving access to mental health resources for families.

Emily Rempel and Erin McCloskey present at IPDLN 2024 in Chicago

The CDC were represented by two Public Participation & Involvement researchers at the International Population Data Linkage Network Conference in Chicago in September 2024. Emily Rempel presented on the recent Round Ere project with her presentation titled 'Round 'Ere: Developing a novel method to engage community on the design of wellbeing data hubs.' More information on this project can be found on the website ([Round 'Ere - Civic Data Cooperative](#)). Erin McCloskey's poster presentation was titled 'Centering the voices of people living with multimorbidity to develop visual dashboards to facilitate structured medication reviews: the role of patient and public involvement and engagement in the DynAIRx study.' Her reflections on the conference are below.

"Presenting at the International Population Data Linkage Network (IPDLN) conference in September was a highly valuable experience for me as a researcher. It was the first time I presented at a conference following the birth of my son and coming back from maternity leave. Taking part in the poster session was pivotal in reigniting my confidence to present my work to an international audience. This experience gave me the opportunity to practice my communication skills by honing my ability to communicate a complex study like DynAIRx to a diverse audience. It also increased my own visibility within the research landscape. IPDLN offered an opportunity to connect to a wide network of researchers which expanded my perspective on population data. Furthermore, it gave me ideas to explore interdisciplinary approaches to make this area of research more accessible to the public."

Celebrating one year of CHIL

The Civic Health Innovation Labs (CHIL) mark their first anniversary this month! They've launched key health innovation projects, strengthened international collaborations, secured funding and hosted Professor Sir Chris Whitty among many highlights this year. The CDC are pleased to be a part of CHILs story and look forward to more exciting events and collaborations in 2025. For more information on the Year of CHIL click below to view the University of Liverpool's story. [Stories - Civic Health Innovation Labs \(CHIL\) - University of Liverpool](#)

Looking ahead to 2025

The CDC has lots of exciting ongoing and new projects planned for the coming year.

In addition to the projects and events mentioned above, we are launching '**Greater Data**', working alongside Capacity to test the blue print for finding data solutions for public service challenges. We'll be doing further innovation work to launch data skills meets, a second hackathon and writing reports on data governance and skills in the region.

We'll be working with the **Digital Commons Policy Council** to host a hybrid 2-day event in May 2025, welcoming in-person delegates to Liverpool.

Working alongside the **Student Enterprise** team we will be running another iteration of the programme.

The CDC are also launching a **Podcast** in January 2025, in this six-part podcast series, our presenter explores the rapidly evolving world of artificial intelligence (AI) and its impact on healthcare, democracy, and society, focusing on the Liverpool City Region. Each episode delves into key issues such as AI's role in clinical settings, the democratisation of data innovation, regulation of powerful tech companies, the biases embedded in AI systems, and regional disparities in AI benefits. Through thought-provoking discussions with healthcare professionals, data ethicists, policy experts, local leaders, and the people of Liverpool, the series offers listeners insights into how AI is shaping our present and future. Engaging, accessible, and relevant, AI & Us encourages listeners to reflect on the kind of future we want to build with AI—and how we can ensure it benefits everyone—more details on the Podcast launch will follow!

We've submitted application for abstracts and panels for several different conferences and are hoping to host an event when the **British Science Festival** visits Liverpool in September 2025.

If any of these projects are of interest to you, we would be more than happy to share more information or look at ways in which you can get involved. Please see our contact details below.

Thank you all for your interest, involvement, and valuable contributions to the CDC in 2024, we look forward to working with you again in the coming year!

Have a restful Christmas and a Happy New Year from the CDC Team!

Contact Us

We believe that by working in collaboration with innovative and trusted organisations we can positively impact our region's health and wellbeing. Our mission is to enable positive change in health and wellbeing through data and cooperation. We're here to answer any questions you may have about our organisation, how we interact with data and how we impact the Liverpool City Region.

If you have questions, please get in touch with our team who will be able to assist you. If you're looking to talk to us about a potential partnership, visit our [partner with us](#) page.

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